

Study of Quantum Zeno Effect using IBM Quantum Experience

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UNDERTAKING

We declare that the work presented in this project titled “**Study of Quantum Zeno Effect using IBM Quantum Experience**”, submitted to the Department of Physics and Astronomical Science, School of Basic and Applied Sciences, Central university of Jammu, Samba-181143, India, for the award of the Degree of Bachelor in Science (Hons.) in Physics Under scheme Integrated B.Sc. (Hons)-M.Sc. in Physics, is our original work. We have not plagiarized or submitted the same work for the award of any other degree. In case this undertaking is found incorrect, We accept that my degree may be unconditionally withdrawn.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the dissertation entitled “**Study of Quantum Zeno Effect using IBM Quantum Experience**” has been submitted by **Shahnawaz Ansari** and **Hema Ram** has been carried out under my supervision in partial fulfillment of the requirement for the degree of Bachelor of Science (H) in Physics.

I certify that they had carried out their record of research work independently has not been submitted elsewhere for a degree.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Quantum Zeno Effect (QZE) has been one of the most interesting phenomena in quantum mechanics ever since its discovery in 1977 by B. Mishra and E. C. G. Sudarshan (1). There have been many attempts for experimental realization of the same. Here we simulate a two level system for Rabi-driven oscillation and then disturb the time evolution by intermediate repetitive measurements using quantum gates to increase the survival probability of the qubit in initial state. The circuits are designed along with the added intermediate measurements and executed on IBM Quantum Simulator, and the outcomes are shown to be consistent with the predictions. The increasing survival probability with the number of intermediate measurements demonstrates the QZE. Furthermore some alternate explanations for the obtained results are provided which leads to some ambiguity in giving the exact reasoning for the observed outcomes

Quantum Zeno Effect (QZE) says that if we do repeated measurements on an unstable quantum system then we can slow down the quantum mechanical evolution of the system. In simple term the QZE refers to a slowing down of the evolution of a quantum state in the limit that the state is observed continuously.

The QZE is a quantum mechanical phenomenon first described by George Sudarshan and Baidyanath Mishra in 1977 article "The Zeno's Paradox in Quantum Theory". They studied the evolution of quantum system subjected to frequent ideal measurements. They showed that in the limit of infinitely frequent measurements, a quantum system would remain in its initial state. The experimental demonstration of Quantum Zeno Effect on real system was done in IHBW Experiment (2, 3).

The IHBW Experiment:

The experiment of Itano, Heinzen, Bollinger and Wineland observes the Quantum Zeno Effect in a three level atom. Level 1 and level 2 are stable on the time scale of the experiment. Level 3 decays to level 1 with the emission of a photon. In the experiment of IHBW, level 1 and 2 were two of the hyperfine sub-levels of the ground state (2s) of the Be^+ ion. Level 3 was a sublevel of the 2p excited state that decayed only to level 1.

The experiment was carried out with a sample of about 5000+ Be^+ ions confined by electric and magnetic field in a penning trap. The steps in the experiment were as follows:-

- 1) The ions were prepared in level 1 by optical pumping with the laser beam.
- 2) A resonant radio frequency (RF) magnetic field was applied for the interval required to drive the ions to the level 2.

- 3) During the time that RF pulse was applied, a variable number n of equally spaced short laser pulses was applied to the ions.
- 4) The laser (resonant with the 1 to 3 transition) was turned on, and the induced fluorescence was recorded.

The intensity of laser induced fluorescence at the end of the experiment was proportional to the population of level 1. If there are no optical pulses during the long RF pulse, then all the population is transferred from level 1 to level 2.

Figure 1 Energy level diagram for the IHBW demonstration of QZE. A resonant field drives transitions between levels 1 and 2.

Figure 2 timing of the radio frequency and optical fields applied to beryllium ions in the IHBW experiment. Short 'measurement' pulses with the 1-to-3 transition interrupt the 1-to-2 transition driven by a single, long RF pulse.

Figure 3 probability of making 1-to-2 transition as a function of n number of optical 'measurement' pulses. Data are indicated by bars with horizontal stripes. Simple calculation (cal. 1) is indicated by solid bars and improved calculation (cal.2) by bars with diagonal stripes.

II. Theory

The simplest non-trivial quantum mechanical example for explaining QZE would be the two-level system. Let us consider the well known Rabi oscillation for a two-level system caused by a generic Hamiltonian of the form $\hat{H} = \Omega(|0\rangle\langle 1| + |1\rangle\langle 0|)$ where Ω is a time-independent constant. This Hamiltonian takes the qubit from state $|0\rangle$ to $|1\rangle$ and from state $|1\rangle$ to $|0\rangle$ and its matrix form looks like:

$$\hat{H} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \Omega \\ \Omega & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Clearly then, $\hat{H}|0\rangle = \Omega|1\rangle$ and $\hat{H}|1\rangle = \Omega|0\rangle$. We can exponentiate this Hamiltonian to find the time evolution operator as:

$$\hat{U} = e^{-i\hat{H}t} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos(\Omega t) & -i \sin(\Omega t) \\ -i \sin(\Omega t) & \cos(\Omega t) \end{pmatrix}$$

It can be easily seen that if \hat{U} acts on the initial state $|0\rangle$ then it would result in a superposition of states $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$.

$$\hat{U}|0\rangle = \cos(\Omega t)|0\rangle - i \sin(\Omega t)|1\rangle$$

From above equation the survival probability, P_s of staying in state $|0\rangle$ after time 't' is $\cos^2(\Omega t)$. We can further write:

$$\begin{aligned} P_s &= \cos^2(\Omega t) = \frac{1}{2}(1 + \cos(2\Omega t)) \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + 1 - \frac{(2\Omega t)^2}{2!} + \frac{(2\Omega t)^4}{4!} - \dots \right) \end{aligned}$$

Neglecting the higher order terms by considering t to be small we obtain:

$$P_s = \frac{1}{2} \left(2 - \frac{(2\Omega t)^2}{2!} \right) = 1 - \Omega^2 t^2$$

Now, if we divide t to ' n ' intervals and measure after each interval then after the final n^{th} interval's measurement the survival probability becomes:

$$P_s = \left(1 - \Omega^2 \left(\frac{t}{n}\right)^2\right)^n$$

Considering $\frac{t}{n}$ to be very small as compared to 1 we can further write as:

$$P_s = 1 - \frac{\Omega^2 t^2}{n}$$

Above equation clearly shows that the survival probability increases with the number of intervals or the number of intermediate measurements n and with increasing value of n the survival probability tends towards unity.

$$P_s \propto n \text{ and}$$

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} P_s = 1$$

III. Implementation on IBM quantum experience

Setting up the basic circuit:-

On the QE platform, we have used U3 gates as time evolution operator and CNOT gates as the intermediate disturbances while the states $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$ as the initial and final states of the desired two level system respectively. To implement the theoretical formulation on IBM QE the primary task is to prepare the desired initial state and the unitary time evolution operator. IBM QE initializes all the qubits in the state $|0\rangle$. For the unitary time evolution we use the U3 gate provided on IBM QE; we set the parameters θ, ϕ and λ as per our requirement to simulate \hat{U} . The U3 gate on IBM QE has the following form:

$$U3(\theta, \phi, \lambda) = \begin{pmatrix} \cos(\frac{\theta}{2}) & e^{-i\lambda} \sin(\frac{\theta}{2}) \\ e^{i\phi} \sin(\frac{\theta}{2}) & e^{i(\lambda+\phi)} \cos(\frac{\theta}{2}) \end{pmatrix}$$

Thus by choosing the parameters $\phi = -\pi/2, \lambda = \pi/2$ and $\theta = 2\Omega t$, we make U3 equals to \hat{U} (4). Now we can operate \hat{U} on state $|0\rangle$ i.e. to implement U3 on qubit q[0] as shown:

Figure 4 Circuit describing the operation of U3 on q[0] qubit where, the U3 has the value of $\phi = -\pi/2, \lambda = \pi/2$ and $\theta = \pi/2$.

Figure 5 Probability for state $|0\rangle$ is= 50.464% and for $|1\rangle$ is = 49.536%

The measurement box added to the circuit after U3 gate in above figure measures the qubit q[0]. If we choose $\theta = \pi/2$ then q[0] is measured to be found in $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$ with roughly equal probability of 50% as shown in above figure which is in fact what we would expect theoretically.

Adding the intermediate measurements:-

To observe the QZE, we add the CNOT gates as the intermediate disturbances dividing the measurement interval to equal halves. For $n = 2$, we use two U3 gates each having $\theta = \pi/4$. The values of ϕ and λ are kept unchanged. Further we add one CNOT gate right after each U3 gate and at the end we put the measurement box in the qubit line of q[0].

We have used here the result that operating one U3 gate with $\theta = \pi/2$ is equivalent to operating two U3 gates with $\theta = \pi/4$ and to generalize it we can say that operating one U3 gate with $\theta = \pi/m$ is equal to operating n U3 gates sequentially with $\theta = (\pi/m)/n = \pi/mn$.

To give specific example, we start with $m = 2$ and $n = 8$. This particularly refers to using 8 U3 gates sequentially each having $\theta = \pi/16$. The circuit and its measurement outcomes are shown in below figure. It can be seen that the survival probability is found to be **51.46%** which is in close agreement with the result obtained in fig. 5 i.e., for a single U3 gate with $\theta = \pi/2$.

Figure 6 circuit with 8 U3 gates each gate with $\theta = \pi/16$.

Figure 7 plot showing the 50% probability of getting state $|0\rangle$ here shows that 8 U3 gates of $\theta = \pi/16$ is equivalent to one U3 gate of $\theta = \pi/2$.

Now, we add intermediate measurements 'n' for specific value of $m = 2$ and observe the survival probability of state $|0\rangle$.

For $n = 2$

To observe the QZE, we add the intermediate disturbances dividing the measurement interval to equal halves. For $n = 2$, we use two U3 gates each having $\theta = \pi/4$. The resulting circuit is as follow:

Figure 8 Quantum circuit for $n = 2$. The circuit describes the operation of two U3 gates and two CNOT gates on q[0] where, each of U3 has the value of $\phi = -\pi/2, \lambda = \pi/2$ and $\theta = \pi/4$.

Figure 9 Measurement outcomes of q[0] after the operation of two U3 gates with parameters $\phi = -\pi/2, \lambda = \pi/2$ and $\theta = \pi/4$ and two CNOT gates, which gives probability for $|0\rangle = 75\%$.

We can clearly see the effect of adding one intermediate measurement; the survival probability goes to roughly **75%** from **50%**.

Next, we keep increasing the value of n in our quantum circuit gradually and with each increment of n we put one extra U3 gate along with one extra CNOT gate by taking $\theta = \pi/2n$. We put the measurement gate at the end.

For $n = 3$

for $n = 3$, we take three U3 gates each having $\theta = \pi/6$ and followed by a CNOT gate as shown:

Figure 10 Quantum circuit for $n = 3$. The circuit describes the operation of three U3 gates and three CNOT gates on $q[0]$ where, each of U3 has the value of $\phi = -\pi/2, \lambda = \pi/2$ and $\theta = \pi/6$.

Figure 11 Measurement outcomes of $q[0]$ after the operation of three U3 gates with parameters $\phi = -\pi/2, \lambda = \pi/2$ and $\theta = \pi/6$ and three CNOT gates, which gives probability for state $|0\rangle = 83.40\%$

It can be seen from above result that for three intermediate measurements the survival probability becomes **83.40%**.

For $n = 4$

Similarly for $n = 4$, we take four U3 gates each having $\theta = \pi/8$ and followed by CNOT gates as follow:

Figure 12 Quantum circuit for $n = 4$. The circuit describes the operation of four U3 gates and four CNOT gates on q[0] where, each of U3 has the value of $\phi = -\pi/2, \lambda = \pi/2$ and $\theta = \pi/8$.

Figure 13 Measurement outcomes of q[0] after the operation of four U3 gates with parameters $\phi = -\pi/2, \lambda = \pi/2$ and $\theta = \pi/8$ and four CNOT gates, which gives probability for state $|0\rangle = 87.11\%$.

It can be clearly seen from above result that for four intermediate measurements the survival probability becomes approx **87.11%**.

For $n = 5$

Similarly for $n = 5$, we take five U3 gates each having $\theta = \pi/10$ and followed by CNOT gates as follow:

Figure 14 Quantum circuit for $n = 5$. The circuit describes the operation of five U3 gates and five CNOT gates on $q[0]$ where, each of U3 has the value of $\phi = -\pi/2, \lambda = \pi/2$ and $\theta = \pi/10$.

Figure 15 Measurement outcomes of $q[0]$ after the operation of five U3 gates with parameters $\phi = -\pi/2, \lambda = \pi/2$ and $\theta = \pi/10$ and five CNOT gates, which gives probability for state $|0\rangle = 89.84\%$.

We can clearly see the effect of adding five intermediate measurements; the survival probability becomes approximately **89.84%**.

For $n = 14$

We take measurements until $n = 14$ and the result for fourteen intermediate measurements is as follows:

Figure 16 Measurement outcomes of $q[0]$ after the operation of fourteen U3 gates with parameters $\phi = -\pi/2$, $\lambda = \pi/2$ and $\theta = \pi/28$ and fourteen CNOT gates, which gives probability for state $|0\rangle = 96.00\%$.

We can clearly see the effect of adding $n = 14$ intermediate measurements; the survival probability goes to roughly **96%** from **50%**.

Thus we can conclude that as we increase the intermediate measurements, the survival probability approaches to **100%**.

The meaning of measurement here:

The principle of deferred and implicit measurement says that if we leave some quantum wires untouched we can assume they are measured (5). Based on this principle, we can treat each intermediate CNOT gate as an intermediate measurement and thus it is these intermediate CNOT gates, which causes the increase in survival probability.

IV. Result

The resulting plot of survival probabilities against their corresponding n for five different sets of θ values; $\theta = \pi/2, \pi/3, \pi/4, \pi/5, \pi/6$ or $m = 2, 3, 4, 5$ and 6 is as follows:

Figure 17 The plot of survival probability versus number of intermediate measurements (n). The series 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 correspond to the θ values $\pi/2, \pi/3, \pi/4, \pi/5$, and $\pi/6$ respectively. The curve for a lower θ values saturates faster as its initial survival probability (for $n = 1$) of it is higher.

It is very conspicuous from above figure that the survival probability increases continuously with n and then saturates close to **100%** for higher value of n . This demonstrates the Quantum Zeno Effect.

V. Conclusion

We have shown here that the survival probability of a qubit staying in state $|0\rangle$ increases with the number of intermediate measurements. In other words, we have suppressed the transition of the qubit from state $|0\rangle$ to $|1\rangle$. From this point of view, the observed behavior in figure 17 seems to demonstrate Quantum Zeno Effect (QZE). In doing so, we have accomplished the objective of this project.

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